

Linus Pauling and vitamin C, and biographies of Linus Pauling

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Location of this document:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20374065> 2026-6-16

The purpose of this list was to collect Linus Pauling's texts on vitamin C and the common cold, and separately his other vitamin and nutrition related texts. The second purpose was to list major biographies of Pauling. Finally, at the end of this document there is a brief summary of Pauling's work on the vitamin C and the common cold.

This document does not provide any new comments on the dozens of randomized trials on vitamin C for the common cold; there are several published statistical analyses of trial findings.² In addition, this document does not discuss the conflict between Pauling and mainstream medicine; several published analyses consider biases against vitamin C.³

Contents	Page
List of publications by Pauling	2
Pauling L (1970) Vitamin C and the Common Cold	3
Pauling L (1976) Vitamin C, the Common Cold, and the Flu	7
Pauling's papers on vitamin C and the common cold	9
Other vitamin and nutrition related papers by Pauling	12
Pauling's own recollections	20
Biographies of Pauling	22
Linus Pauling, vitamin C, and the common cold	28

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<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/persons/harri-hemil%C3%A4>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä.

2 **Major publications on vitamin C and the common cold:**

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/41424103> 2026 Common cold trials were ignored in UK recommendations

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39803741> 2025 Vitamin C for the common cold and pneumonia

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38082300> 2023 Vitamin C reduces the severity of common colds

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28353648> 2017 Vitamin C and infections

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23440782> 2013 Cochrane review: Vitamin C for the common cold

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24279478> 2013 Vitamin C and common cold-induced asthma

<https://zenodo.org/records/6395596> 2006 Thesis: Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections?

3 **Bias against vitamin C in mainstream medicine:**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; critiques by Hemilä

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455> 2022 Bias against vitamin C in mainstream medicine

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223748> 1997 Was Linus Pauling right or wrong?

<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/7979> 1996 Problems with inaccurate reviews

<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/8082> 1996 A case study of how preconceptions influence the analysis of results

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/42358> 1995 A retrospective analysis of Chalmers' review

<https://zenodo.org/records/6395596> 2006 Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections?

List of publications by Pauling

The Publications of Professor Linus Pauling (1996)

Zelek S Herman and DB Munro

<https://zenodo.org/records/20268631>

<https://www.girinst.org/~zeke/test.bit.pdf>

The Herman-Munro numbering is indicated by brackets [] after Pauling's publications.

Oregon State University

Ava Helen and Linus Pauling Papers

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling>

Oregon State University

Linus Pauling Biography

<https://lpi.oregonstate.edu/about/linus-pauling-biography>

Linus Pauling online

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/digitalresources/pauling>

Linus Pauling's research notebooks, 46 vols

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/>

National Library of Medicine

The Linus Pauling Papers

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/spotlight/mm>

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/spotlight/mm/feature/medicine>

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/spotlight/mm/feature/additional-resources>

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/spotlight/mm/browse>

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/spotlight/mm/browse/all-images>

Pauling L (1970a) Vitamin C and the Common Cold. [623]

San Francisco: Freeman

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vitamin_C_and_the_Common_Cold_\(book\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vitamin_C_and_the_Common_Cold_(book))

<https://archive.org/details/vitaminccommonco00paul>

https://archive.org/details/bwb_C0-ACN-753

PBK (1971) Phi Beta Kappa book award:

1971: *Vitamin C and the Common Cold* by Linus Pauling (W. H. Freeman)

<https://www.pbk.org/awards/bookawards/science-winners>

<https://www.pbk.org>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Phi_Beta_Kappa

“The Phi Beta Kappa Society (ΦBK) is the oldest academic honor society in the United States. Founded in 1776 at the College of William & Mary in Virginia...”

Book Reviews and comments:

Am J Publ Health 1971;61:649-51

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1529794>

Atlantic Monthly 2000;(Oct):16-18

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X281>

BMJ 1972a;3:582

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1785845>

BMJ 1972b;4:786

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1786999>

BMJ 1973;3:311-2

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1586487>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/25420949>

BMJ 1976;1:606-7

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1639003>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/20409008>

Bull NY Acad Med 1971;475:532-5

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1749895>

CMAJ 1971a;104:832-5

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1930997/?page=3>

CMAJ 1971b;105:355-7, 363

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1931101>

Pauling's (1971c) response CMAJ 1971;105:448-50

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1931292>

CMAJ 1971c;105:450

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1931277>

CMAJ 1971d;105:901-2

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1931718>

CMAJ 1972a;106:307

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1940396>

CMAJ 1972b;107:479-80

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1940927>

CMAJ 1973;108:835

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1941309>

J R Coll Gen Pract 1971;21:310

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2156371>

JAMA 1971a;215:1506

<https://zenodo.org/records/20156838>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1971.03180220086028>

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X138>

Pauling's (1971d) response JAMA 1971;216:332

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/5107925>

<https://zenodo.org/records/20157562>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1971.03180280086025>

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X140>

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X139> (cover letter)

JAMA 1971b;216:337

<https://zenodo.org/records/20157133>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1971.03180280091036>

Med J Aust 1971a;1:1344-5

<https://zenodo.org/records/20157844>

<https://doi.org/10.5694/j.1326-5377.1971.tb88140.x>

Med J Aust 1971b;1:1361-2

<https://zenodo.org/records/20158238>

<https://doi.org/10.5694/j.1326-5377.1971.tb50331.x>

Nature 1971;230:298-9

<https://zenodo.org/records/20158506>

<https://doi.org/10.1038/230298b0>

Yale J Biol Med 1971;44:230-1

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2591715>

Noren (1970)

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X263>

Davidson (1979) Review in a textbook on nutrition.

<https://zenodo.org/records/20345034>

Passmore (1986) Review in a textbook on nutrition.

<https://zenodo.org/records/20158811>

New York Times:

Blakeslee S (1970 Nov 19) Vitamin C called cold preventive.

<https://www.nytimes.com/1970/11/19/archives/vitamin-c-called-cold-preventive-pauling-says-large-doses-can-ward.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1970/11/19/76793997.html?pageNumber=35>

Editorial (1970 Nov 30) Preventing the common cold.

<https://www.nytimes.com/1970/11/30/archives/preventing-the-common-cold.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1970/11/30/76800339.html?pageNumber=40>

Pauling's response:

Vitamin C and the cold. New York Times, p.44 (15 Dec. 1970).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20714745>

<https://www.nytimes.com/1970/12/15/archives/letters-to-the-editor.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1970/12/15/78821533.html?>

[pageNumber=44](https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1970/12/15/78821533.html?pageNumber=44)

Brody JE (1970 Dec 5) Vitamin C sales booming despite skepticism on Pauling cold cure.

<https://www.nytimes.com/1970/12/05/archives/vitamin-c-sales-booming-despite-skepticism-on-pauling-cold-cure.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1970/12/05/355170672.html?pageNumber=44>

Brody JE (1970 Dec 6) Colds: Vitamin C is latest contender as possible cure.

<https://www.nytimes.com/1970/12/06/archives/medicine-colds-vitamin-c-is-latest-contender-as-possible-cure.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1970/12/06/105324997.html?pageNumber=249>

Diehl HS (1970-12-26) Vitamin C: Cure for Cold?

<https://www.nytimes.com/1970/12/26/archives/letters-to-the-editor.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1970/12/26/355829942.html?pageNumber=16>

Pauling's response:

Vitamin C Controversy. New York Times, p.32 (26 Jan. 1971).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20714972>

<https://www.nytimes.com/1971/01/26/archives/vitamin-c-controversy.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1971/01/26/81871660.html?>

[pageNumber=32](https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1971/01/26/81871660.html?pageNumber=32)

Brody JE (1971 Nov. 28) Vitamin C study rebuts Pauling.

<https://www.nytimes.com/1971/11/28/archives/vitamin-c-study-rebuts-pauling-no-prevention-or-relief-of-common.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1971/11/28/82218227.html?pageNumber=77>

Pauling's response:

Vitamin C undefeated. New York Times, p.24 (30 Dec. 1971).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20714835>

<https://www.nytimes.com/1971/12/30/archives/vitamin-c-undefeated.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1971/12/30/79412517.html?>

[pageNumber=24](https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1971/12/30/79412517.html?pageNumber=24)

Schmeck HM (1975 Mar. 11) Two reports find little merit in using vitamin C to treat colds.

<https://www.nytimes.com/1975/03/11/archives/2-reports-find-little-merit-in-using-vitamin-c-to-treat-colds.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1975/03/11/78827425.html?pageNumber=14>

Pauling's response:

Linus Pauling on vitamin C. New York Times, p.IV:18 (6 April 1975).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20715072>

<https://www.nytimes.com/1975/04/06/archives/letters-to-the-editor.html>
[https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1975/04/06/83171279.html?
pageNumber=206](https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1975/04/06/83171279.html?pageNumber=206)

Pauling L (1976a) Vitamin C, the Common Cold, and the Flu. [741]

San Francisco: Freeman

<https://archive.org/details/vitamincommonco00linu>

Expanded edition: (1981) Vitamin C, the Common Cold, and the Flu. NY: Berkley [850]

Additional section p.158-66

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20717015>

Book-reviews:

Tyrrell DAJ. Cure For All Ills? Review of Vitamin C, The Common Cold, And The Flu, by L. Pauling. British Medical Journal 1977;1:1273–3

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1607103>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/20414404>

Pitkow HS. Review of Vitamin C, the Common Cold, and the Flu, by L. Pauling. American Biology Teacher 1977;39(4):251–2

<https://doi.org/10.2307/4445899>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/4445899>

Lasagna L. Review of Vitamin C, the Common Cold, and the Flu, by L. Pauling. Quarterly Review of Biology 1977;52(4):469–9

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/2823432>

<https://doi.org/10.1086/410304>

J R Coll Gen Pract 1978;28:116

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2158709>

Any Questions? British Medical Journal 1981;283:654–62

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/29503479>

Pauling L (1986a) How to Live Longer and Feel Better. [930]

NY: Freeman.

<https://archive.org/details/howtolivelongerf00paul>

<https://archive.org/details/howtolivelongerf00linu>

Section “Organized Medicine and the Vitamins”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20660210>

Book-reviews:

Nelson M. Nature 1986;320:641

<https://doi.org/10.1038/320641a0>

<https://www.nature.com/nature/journal/v320/n6063/pdf/320641a0.pdf>

Molotsky L. Science Teacher 1988;55:80

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/24142826>

Garrow JS. BMJ 1986;292:1518

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/29523443>

Cameron E and Pauling L (1979) Cancer and vitamin C. [803]

Palo Alto, CA: Linus Pauling Institute of Science and Medicine

<https://archive.org/details/cancervitaminc00came>

<https://archive.org/details/cancervitamincdi00came>

Updated edition (1993) [1075]

<https://archive.org/details/cancervitamincdi0000came>

Preface to the Updated Edition; Summary

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20611299>

For the context of this work, see the biographical list:

Richards E (1988) The politics of therapeutic evaluation: The vitamin C and cancer controversy.

Richards E (1991) Vitamin C and Cancer: Medicine or Politics?

Pauling's papers on vitamin C and the common cold

This list is restricted to papers that are available via the web. In the Herman-Munro list of publications by Pauling, there are several further vitamin C and the common cold publications but most of those not included were popular and published in newspapers or in minor journals.

The brackets [] indicate the number in the Herman-Munro list.

Pauling's major papers on vitamin C and the common cold are 1971a,b, 1976a,b.

Pauling described his motivation to write the *Vitamin C and the Common Cold* in a text published in 1995a: “Here's this man, this professor—I didn't identify him when I wrote my book—Victor Herbert,⁴ who to this day keeps writing papers and giving speeches saying that no one benefits from taking extra vitamins ... and he won't even look at the evidence.

The upshot of this whole thing is that I finally became sufficiently irritated by this fellow that I decided I ought to do something about it. So I sat down one summer—here, downstairs in my study—and in two months wrote a book Vitamin C and the Common Cold.”

Pauling L (1970) Vitamin C and the cold. New York Times, p. 44 (15 Dec. 1970) [627]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20714745>

<https://www.nytimes.com/1970/12/15/archives/letters-to-the-editor.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1970/12/15/78821533.html?pageNumber=44>

Pauling (1971) Vitamin C Controversy. New York Times, p. 24 (26 Jan. 1971) [none]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20714972>

<https://www.nytimes.com/1971/01/26/archives/vitamin-c-controversy.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1971/01/26/81871660.html?pageNumber=32>

Pauling L (1971a) The significance of the evidence about ascorbic acid and the common cold. PNAS 68(11):2678-81 [638]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4941984>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC389499>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/61202>

Manuscript:

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X101>

Pauling L (1971b) Ascorbic acid and the common cold. Am J Clin Nutr 24(11):1294-9 [632]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4940368>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/24.11.1294>

Pauling L (1971c) Vitamin C and the common cold. CMAJ 105:448-50 [636]

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1931292>

Comment on CMAJ 1971b:

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1931101>

4 Victor Herbert, hematologist.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Victor_Herbert (hematologist)

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(03\)12336-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(03)12336-7)

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/77.4.757>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/134.7.1678>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/ajh.10306>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/26.9.907>

Flaws described in a paper by Victor Herbert:

Hemilä H. The good and harm of vitamin C. Nutrition Today 1994;29:49-50.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/00017285-199403000-00008>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/135155>

Pauling (1971) Vitamin C undefeated. New York Times, p. 24 (30 Dec. 1971) [639]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20714835>
<https://www.nytimes.com/1971/12/30/archives/vitamin-c-undefeated.html>
<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1971/12/30/79412517.html?pageNumber=24>

Pauling L (1971d) Vitamin C and common cold. JAMA 216(2):332 [640]
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/5107925>
<https://zenodo.org/records/20157562>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1971.03180280086025>

Manuscript:

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X140>
<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X139> (cover letter)

Comment on JAMA 1971a:

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1971.03180220086028>
<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X138>

Pauling (1972) Vitamin C. Science 177:1152 [653]
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17847190>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.177.4055.1152>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.177.4055.1152.a>
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/1734246>

Comment related to the letter above:

Edsall (1972) Linus Pauling and vitamin C. Science 178:696
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.178.4062.696.b>

Pauling L (1973) Ascorbic acid and the common cold.
Scottish Medical Journal 18(1):1-2 [661]
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4577802>
<https://doi.org/10.1177/003693307301800101>
<https://zenodo.org/records/20345629>

(1973) “Professor Linus Pauling has drawn our attention to certain inconsistencies in some of the figures that appeared in our recent paper ‘Vitamin C and the common cold: a double-blind trial’ (Can Med Assoc J 107: 503, 1972).”
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1941144>

Pauling L (1974) Early evidence about vitamin C and the common cold.
Journal of Orthomolecular Psychiatry 3(3):139-51 [680]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20613499>
<https://www.orthomolecular.org/library/jom/1974/pdf/1974-v03n03-p139.pdf>
https://isom.ca/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/JOM_1974_03_3_02_Early_Evidence_About_Vitamin_C_And_the_Common_Cold.pdf

Pauling L (1975a) The cold war. TIME Magazine (Mar 31) [none]
<https://time.com/archive/6817175/forum-the-cold-war>

See Anonymous (1975) at the end references

Pauling L (1975) Linus Pauling on vitamin C. New York Times, p. IV:18 (6 April 1975) [698]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20715072>
<https://www.nytimes.com/1975/04/06/archives/letters-to-the-editor.html>
<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1975/04/06/83171279.html?pageNumber=206>

Pauling (1976a) Ascorbic acid and the common cold: Evaluation of its efficacy and toxicity. Part I. Medical Tribune 17(12):18-9 [722]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11546757>

This is commentary on Dykes and Meier (1975) review on vitamin C and the common cold in JAMA. The paper was rejected by JAMA even after Dr. Pauling twice made revisions to meet the suggestions of its referees.

The Dykes-Meier review:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1089817>

Pauling (1976b) Ascorbic acid and the common cold. Part II.

Medical Tribune 17(13):37-8 [723]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11547088>

Pauling L (1976) On fighting swine flu. New York Times, p. 24 (5 June 1976) [727]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20715190>

<https://www.nytimes.com/1976/06/05/archives/letters-to-the-editor.html>

<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1976/06/05/75611652.html?pageNumber=19>

Pauling L (1979) Ascorbic acid. Lancet 313:615 [789]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/85208>

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(79\)91048-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(79)91048-1)

Comments on: (1979);313:308:

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(79\)90716-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(79)90716-5)

Pauling L (1981) Some problems with controlled clinical trials: The barracks effect.

In: Expanded edition: (1981) Vitamin C, the Common Cold, and the Flu. NY: Berkley [850]

Additional section p.158-66

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20717015>

Pauling L (1995a) Pauling's reason for writing *Vitamin C and the Common Cold*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20343221>

Other vitamin and nutrition related papers by Pauling

This list is restricted to papers that are available via the web. In the list of publications by Pauling, there are several further vitamin publications but most of those not included are popular and in minor journals. The brackets [] indicate the number in the Herman-Munro list.

Pauling L (1958) The relation between longevity and obesity in human beings.

PNAS 44(6):619-22 [382]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16590251>

Pauling L (1962) The molecular nature of mental disease. [none]

Manuscript:

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X229>

Pauling L (1962) Chemistry of mental disease. [none]

Manuscript:

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X87>

Pauling L (1968) Orthomolecular psychiatry. Varying the concentrations of substances normally present in the human body may control mental disease. Science 160:265-71 [588=658]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/5641253>

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.160.3825.265>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/1723748>

<https://zenodo.org/records/20611720>

Manuscript:

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X137>

Pauling L (1968) Vitamin therapy: treatment for the mentally ill. Science 160:1181-2 [593]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/5648257>

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.160.3833.1181-a>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/1724571>

Pauling L (1968) Orthomolecular somatic and psychiatric medicine.

Zeitschrift Vitalstoffe-Zivilisationskrankheiten 12:3-5 [596]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20610454>

Pauling L (1970) Evolution and the need for ascorbic acid. PNAS 67(4):1643-8 [619]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/5275366>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC283405>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/60547>

Pauling L (1971) Orthomolecular psychiatry. Schizophrenia 3:129-33 [631]

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“Travelling by train from Denver to Chicago in 1949, William Castle acquainted Linus Pauling with the facts about sickle cell anemia, a disease Castle thought was due to ‘some type of molecular alignment.’ Thus stimulated, Pauling and his group demonstrated for the first time the molecular consequence of a mutation that causes a genetic disorder (hemoglobin S), and termed sickle cell anemia ‘a molecular disease’.”

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Linus Pauling, vitamin C, and the common cold^{5, 6}

Figure. The numbers of participants over time in placebo-controlled trials for which ≥ 1 g/d of vitamin C was administered. The numbers of participants in studies published over two consecutive years are combined and plotted for the first of the two years.

This figure is from Hemilä and Chalker (2022).

Pauling's 1970 book "*Vitamin C and the Common Cold*" and other activities caused widespread interest in vitamin C in the early 1970s, both among lay people and among academic researchers. As a consequence, 29 placebo-controlled randomized trials were published in the eight-year period from 1972 to 1979. The total number of participants in those trials was 8409, which corresponds to an average of 290 participants per study. After the mid-1970s, interest in vitamin C and the common cold plummeted within a few years. During the 30-year period from 1985 to 2014, only 11 placebo-controlled trials comprising just 538 participants in total were published, with a mean of 49 participants per study. Thus, the number of trials declined from the rate of 3.6/year to 0.37/year, but also, their average size declined by 83%. This rapid decline of interest in vitamin C can be attributed largely to the three flawed papers from the year 1975, as they led to increased bias against vitamin C. The errors in the three 1975 publications are summarized by Hemilä (2006) and by Hemilä and Chalker (2022), which give references to further details.

5 This section was previously published with minor differences in: Hemilä H. Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? p.11-3,28,35-36 <https://zenodo.org/records/6395596> <https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

6 For references to biographies and Pauling's texts, see the preceding section. For other references, see the end of this section. For critiques of erroneous vitamin C papers, see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426>

Table: Three major early vitamin C and common cold trials⁷

Trial	Vitamin C	Placebo	Difference	P(1-tail)
Ritzel (1961,1976)				
Schoolchildren in a skiing camp in Swiss Alps, 1 g/day vit C, 1 week				
Participants	139	140		
Common cold episodes ⁸	17	31	-45%	0.015
Duration of colds, mean	1.8	2.6	-31%	<0.05
Days per group	31	80	-61%	
Constitutional symptoms during the common cold (General malaise, headache, muscle ache, abdominal pain, vomiting, diarrhoea.)				
Cases	8	21	-62%	0.006
Days per group	9	48	-81%	
Cowan et al. (1942)				
Schoolchildren in USA, 0.2 g/day vit C, 4 months				
Participants	208	155		
Cold episodes, mean per person ⁹	1.9 (SD 1.0)	2.2 (SD 1.0)	-14%	0.003
Days lost from school per person ⁸	1.1 (SD 1.1)	1.6 (SD 1.6)	-31%	0.0003
Franz et al. (1956)				
Schoolchildren in USA, 0.2 g/day vit C, 4 months				
Participants ¹⁰	44	45		
Common cold episodes	14	15		
Colds cured or improved in 5 days	13	8	+74%	0.012

⁷ **These 3 placebo-controlled trials were included in the Pauling (1971a) meta-analysis.**

The fourth trial by Wilson et al. was available to Pauling only as an abstract (Wilson and Loh 1969) and the final report was complicated with 48 significance tests, with several outcomes in various subgroups, so that it does not provide unambiguous data, and therefore is not listed here; see Pauling (1971a) for his summary.

This table was published in Hemilä H. Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? p.14

<https://zenodo.org/records/6395596>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

⁸ The number of episodes not being published, it is inferred from the total number of days per group and the average duration (Pauling 1971a).

⁹ Cowan et al. (1942): the SD values for the number of 'cold episodes per person' were calculated from the reported SE values. Cowan et al. did not report the SD or SE for 'days lost from school per person.' In most trials, the SD for common cold duration has been about 70% of the mean duration of colds (Hemilä, Chalker 2013). Here the P-value for 'days lost from school per person' is calculated on the assumption that both SD values are equal to the mean. Cowan reported: "The actual difference between the two groups during the year of the study amounts to one third of a cold per person. Statistical analysis of the data reveals that a difference as large as this would arise only three or four times in a hundred through chance alone".

¹⁰ The Franz et al. trial (1956) had a 2×2 factorial design and the bioflavonoid and no-bioflavonoid groups are combined here. This data is from their tables 1 to 4. Their summary table 5 erroneously records 4 'improved or cured,' for the bioflavonoid group whereas their table 4 gives 5 (= 1 + 4).

Before the 1970s a few physicians had concluded from their own observations that vitamin C administration would be beneficial against the common cold (e.g., Ruskin 1938; Markwell 1947; Bessel-Lorck 1959; Regnier 1968). The authors of the influential Sheffield trial examining the effects of vitamin C deprivation of human subjects concluded that common cold episodes “lasted longer in the deprived group” (Bartley, Krebs and O’Brien 1953 p 43, Hemilä 2025). Some other early controlled trials also indicated that vitamin C intake may affect the common cold, but the results of various trials were not quite consistent and the early positive findings did not affect mainstream medicine.

The notion that vitamin C might be of benefit against colds achieved wide popularity in the 1970s when Linus Pauling wrote a best-selling book entitled *Vitamin C and the Common Cold* in which he claimed that supplementation would prevent and alleviate common cold episodes (Pauling 1970a, 1971c,d, 1976a; Pauling 1995a). In 1971, Pauling’s book received the Phi Beta Kappa award for the best scientific book of the year in the USA (PBK 1971). Pauling’s book made millions of Americans interested in vitamin C supplements and, in the academic world, it led to the initiation of dozens of new trials intended to find out whether Pauling was right or wrong (Figure; Hemilä and Chalker 2022). To understand why Pauling’s book could have such an enormous impact on the vitamin C field, his personal background must be briefly reviewed.

Pauling is widely considered the greatest chemist of the previous century (Greenberg 1984; Lipscomb 1994; Rich 1994,1975; Dunitz 1996, 1997; McConnell 1996; Mason 1997; Nakamura and Csikszentmihalyi 2001). “In 1931, at only thirty years old, the Oregon-raised Linus Pauling knew he was the world’s best chemist. Ten years later the rest of the world’s chemists agreed” (Watson 1999, 2001). “Pauling helped to transform chemistry from a largely phenomenological subject to one based firmly on structural and quantum mechanical principles” (Perutz 1994).

Pauling was also one of the founders of molecular biology (Gray 1949; Judson 1979; Pauling 1986b, 1993; Kay 1989; Crick 1992; Perutz 1994; Rich 1995; Mason 1997; Morgan 1998; Edison 2001; Eisenberg 2003; Gruber and Lupas 2003). Before any protein structures had been solved, Pauling conceived, for example, that biological specificity results from a detailed complementarity in the structure of two molecules. Pauling discovered the basic structural features of proteins, α -helix and β -sheet, and invented the concept of the molecular evolutionary clock. In one of his major papers in 1949, Pauling et al. showed that hemoglobin from patients suffering from sickle cell anemia had a different electric charge from that from healthy individuals, and this laid the groundwork for establishing the field of molecular medicine (Strasser 1999, 2002; Eaton 2003). Pauling received the **Nobel Prize in Chemistry in 1954** (Pauling 1954).

At the end of the Second World War, Pauling served on a presidential committee formed to plot the path of science in the post-war period. The resulting Vannevar Bush Report¹¹ led to the expansion of the National Institutes of Health (NIH), allowing for extramural research funding, and the creation of the National Science Foundation (Paradowski 1996).

In 1946 Pauling joined the Emergency Committee of Atomic Scientists, chaired by Albert Einstein, whose most important task was to make people in all countries aware of the transformation of the world brought about by the development of the atomic bomb. During 1958, Pauling sent a copy of the petition opposing nuclear weapons testing, with endorsement by 11,021 scientists from 49 countries including 40 members of the US National Academy of Sciences, 216 members of the Soviet Academy of Sciences and 36 Nobel Laureates, to Dag Hammarskjöld, the Secretary-General of the United Nations. Public opinion worldwide led to test-ban negotiations in

11 Science, the endless frontier. A report to the President by Vannevar Bush, director of the Office of scientific research and development. July 1945.

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late 1958. On the same day (10th Oct 1963) that the limited test ban treaty signed by the USA, UK, and the USSR went into effect, it was announced that Linus Pauling would be awarded the **Nobel Peace Prize for 1962** (Pauling 1963; Kreisler 1983; Mason 1997; Jolly 2002).

Because Pauling was the best-known American scientist publicly arguing for disarmament, he began to come under attack from right-wing political groups. Because of the pressures of McCarthyism on government officials, Pauling encountered difficulties in obtaining a passport. For example, he was without a passport when his Nobel Prize in Chemistry was announced in 1954, but the Undersecretary of State overruled the Passport Division, enabling him to travel to Sweden to receive his award (Allison 1960; Paradowski 1996; Mason 1997; Nye 1999).

With such a particularly strong background in science and high-level competence in politics, it is obvious that Pauling's 1970 book ***Vitamin C and the Common Cold*** reached extensive readerships in both lay and academic circles and had great impact. Because of Pauling's book, the demand for vitamin C substantially increased. In the USA, the production of vitamin C increased from 8.9 million pounds in 1969 to 11.7 in 1971, corresponding to an increase of 39% in two years and an annual growth rate of 18% (CMR 1972a),¹² in contrast to the annual growth rate of about 6% in the 1960s (CMR 1972c). About 5.6 million pounds of vitamin C were also imported to the US between January and November 1971, up about 160% from the amount imported during the same period in 1970 (CMR 1972b).

In the USA, Pauling personified the issue of vitamin C (Apple 1996). The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) was alarmed by this increasing interest in the consumption of large doses of vitamins, and proposed that over-the-counter sales be restricted to relatively low-potency products, with 'megadoses' requiring a physician's prescription. The health food industry felt threatened and it encouraged customers to protest. Members of the US Congress received more mail on this issue than any other, except for the Vietnam War, and the FDA had to give up their attempt. Why, it was asked, did FDA threaten the sales of vitamins, and do nothing comparable about tobacco and alcohol, whose ill effects in excess were not debatable (Apple 1996). In 1974, Pauling testified in US senate about food supplement legislation (Pauling 1974).

In addition to his book intended for lay people, **Pauling (1971a) carried out a meta-analysis of 4 placebo-controlled trials, which was one of the very first meta-analyses in medicine.**¹³ The results of 3 of the 4 trials are shown in Table. The fourth trial by Wilson et al. (1973a,b,c) was available to Pauling only as an abstract (Wilson and Loh 1969) and the final report was complicated with 48 significance tests, with several outcomes in various subgroups, so that it does not provide unambiguous data (Kinlen and Peto 1973). In his meta-analysis, Pauling combined the P-values of the 4 trials by Fisher's method, concluding that it was highly unlikely that all the reported effects on common cold morbidity from vitamin C supplementation could be explained by chance alone. Pauling (1971a) also pointed out that, out of these 4 trials, the greatest benefit was found by Ritzel (1961; 1976 Brubacher 1989), who used the largest dose, 1 g/day. Pauling thus concluded that gram doses of vitamin C daily would prevent colds in the general population. Pauling (1971b) also carried out a second meta-analysis in which he focused on the two best early trials (Cowan et al. 1942; Ritzel 1961).

Pauling analyzed previously published trials but did not carry out any experimental work on the common cold himself. His book and other activities, however, led to the initiation of several new controlled trials (Figure). Before the 1970s, there was only one trial which used ≥ 1 g/day of vitamin

12 Effect of Linus Pauling's book *Vitamin C and the common cold* on the demand and production of vitamin C. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20558446>

13 Bastian et al. (2010) listed early meta-analyses in medicine. However, in their list they cited the Chalmers meta-analysis (1975) on vitamin C and the common cold, although that had been shown to be severely flawed 15 years before their paper. Bastian et al. did not mention Pauling's meta-analyses (1971a,b) although they were 4 years earlier than the Chalmers (1975) meta-analysis and no flaws have been pointed out in them. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20158813>

C regularly over the trial (Ritzel 1961), but within a decade of Pauling's book about 20 new trials using such high doses regularly over the trial had appeared.

However, the interest in vitamin C and colds disappeared in the middle of the 1970s (Figure). This waning interest was caused by the publication of two negative reviews in wide-circulation journals (Chalmers 1975; Dykes and Meier 1975), and by a particularly influential trial, carried out at the National Institutes of Health (NIH) and published in JAMA, which concluded that the apparent benefits of vitamin C were simply explained by the placebo effect (Karlowski et al. 1975). Thus all these three important negative papers were published the same year. Furthermore, the Karlowski trial (1975) and the Dykes and Meier review (1975) were published in the same issue of JAMA, and Thomas Chalmers was both the principal investigator of the Karlowski, Chalmers, et al. trial (1975; Chalmers 1996) and the author of the other review published in the same year (Chalmers 1975). The importance of these three papers is reflected, for example, by the comment in the TIME magazine: "Three reports now cast a further shadow on Pauling's theory ... that large doses of vitamin C would prevent or cure the common cold" (Anonymous 1975; response by Pauling 1975a). Only a few trials on vitamin C and the common cold were initiated after the middle of the 1970s, after the publication of these three influential papers (Figure).

Since this large set of new trials was carried out, there has been general consensus that vitamin C has no effects on colds, and the three papers published in 1975 are the most usual references for such negative statements (Hemilä 2006, Hemilä and Chalker 2022). For example, based on these three papers,¹⁴ vitamin C was stated to be useless for colds in major textbooks on infectious diseases (Gwaltney 1979, 1985, 1990, 1995; Liu 1989; Cherry 1987, 1992, 1998),¹⁵ in the Cecil Textbook of Medicine (Kapikian 1985; Hendley 1996, 2000),¹⁶ in various textbooks on nutrition (Halsted 1993; Thurnham et al. 2000; Hamilton and Whitney 1982, 1994; Shils et al. 1994),¹⁷ and in the US nutritional recommendations (FNB 1980, 1989a).

The conclusion that vitamin C is useless for colds has also reached the clinicians. For example, a survey of general practitioners in the Netherlands revealed that 47% of respondents considered that homeopathy is efficacious in the treatment of the common cold, whereas only 20% of the respondents considered that vitamin C was (Knipschild et al. 1990). On a scale from 0 to 10, with the high scores corresponding to stronger belief in efficacy, homeopathy for colds received a mean score of 4.7, whereas vitamin C for colds received a mean of only 2.5.

In the UK, 52% of 86 general practitioner trainees considered that homeopathy was useful, whereas only 7% considered large doses of vitamins useful, although no specific indications for usage were presented for either therapy (Reilly 1983). In the USA, 21% of 348 pediatricians considered that homeopathy may be effective, and 21% considered that highdose antioxidant vitamins may be so, but again no indications for usage were presented (Sikand and Laken 1998). Accordingly, the use of vitamin C to treat the common cold comes unambiguously under the

14 See lists:

Major citations to the reviews on vitamin C and the common cold by Chalmers (1975) and by Dykes and Meier (1975).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20344539>

Selected list of papers that cite the Karlowski (1975) trial.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20204507>

See also Tables 1 and 2 and 3 in:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455>

Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C: A list of critiques by Harri Hemilä.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426>

15 Statements on Vitamin C and the Common Cold in Major Infectious Disease Textbooks.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20555885>

16 Statements on Vitamin C and the Common Cold in the Cecil Textbook on Medicine.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20557923>

17 Statements on Vitamin C and the Common Cold in Major Nutrition Textbooks.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20415226>

Eisenberg et al. notion (1993; Dalen 1998) that “medical interventions not taught widely at [US] medical schools or generally available at [US] hospitals” are unconventional or alternative medicine (Turow 1997; Goodwin and Goodwin 1984; Goodwin and Tangum 1998; Louhiala and Hemilä 2014; Hemilä 2017).

Pauling’s meta-analyses on vitamin C and the common cold (1971a,b)

In the 1970s, three meta-analyses on vitamin C and the common cold were published (Pauling 1971a,b; Chalmers 1975). In fact, these three papers were among the first few meta-analyses carried out in medicine. However, the conclusions of these three meta-analyses diverged substantially: for the errors in Chalmers (1975) meta-analysis, see the references associated with that report.

In his first meta-analysis in the *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, Pauling (1971a) analyzed the findings of 4 placebo-controlled trials in which at least 0.1 g/day of vitamin C was administered regularly to the study group (1971a; Table). Pauling combined the P-values derived from 4 placebo-controlled trials by the Fisher method, concluding that there was strong evidence that vitamin C decreased the ‘incidence of colds’ ($P = 0.0014$), and the ‘integrated morbidity’ due to colds ($P = 0.000,022$).

In his second meta-analysis in the *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, Pauling (1971b) focused on the best 2 of the 4 trials (1971b; Cowan et al. 1942; Ritzel 1961). Combining the P-values by the Fisher method led him to conclude that “The null hypothesis of equal effectiveness of ascorbic acid and placebo is rejected at the level P less than 0.001.”

Among the 4 trials included in Pauling’s meta-analysis (1971a; Pauling 1972), the largest dose was used by Ritzel (1961,1976), and Pauling based his quantitative estimations on this trial. Ritzel found that the common cold symptoms in the vitamin C group were 31% shorter and the number of colds 45% lower in the vitamin C group. Pauling also calculated the combination of duration and incidence, ‘integrated morbidity’ referring to the total sickness days per person during the trial, and this was reduced by 61% in the Ritzel trial (Table). Pauling (1971a) then modeled the dose-dependency of vitamin C effect with exponential formulas for which he took constants from the Ritzel trial.

Pauling assumed that the main problem in his estimation was inaccuracy caused by ‘experimental error,’ although he did note that “The values are, of course, expected to depend somewhat on the nature of the population and environment.” However, even with these explicit reservations he was far too optimistic. He could not imagine how great the variations in the results would be in the forthcoming trials. Neither did he consider the possibility that the effects observed by Ritzel may have been caused at least in part by low dietary vitamin C intake, in which case a smaller dose might have produced a similar benefit, and in such a case modeling the vitamin C effect as a function of the supplementary dose would be completely erroneous. Pauling attributed the difference between the study groups entirely to the large dose given to the treatment group. Furthermore, Ritzel carried out his trial with schoolchildren in a skiing school in the Swiss Alps, children who are not a good representative selection of the general population even though technically the trial was good as it was randomized, double-blind and placebo-controlled. Thus, when Pauling extrapolated the results of Ritzel to all people (i.e., to children at school and to adults), he took a bold step and went wrong (Hemilä 1997, Hemilä and Chalker 2013).

Pauling (1971a,b) put much weight on the ‘integrated morbidity’ outcome and summarized the findings of trials by this outcome in his later texts as well (1976a,b,c, 1986a). This measure led Pauling to adhere strongly to the idea of regular supplementation. However, this is not a good combined measure, since the effects on incidence and duration/severity have quite different patterns (Hemilä 1994, Hemilä and Chalker 2013), and it is thus more to the point to analyze these two outcomes separately. Thus, Pauling was qualitatively correct in his conclusion that vitamin C does

affect the duration and severity of colds (Hemilä and Chalker 2023), and probably the incidence of colds in certain specific conditions (Hemilä 1996, 1997), but he was greatly over-optimistic.

It is worth noting that the Ritzel trial (1961) falls to the group of 5 trials with participants under heavy acute physical and/or cold stress that consistently found reduction in common cold incidence (Hemilä 1996, Hemilä and Chalker 2013). Thus, it was not a misjudgment by Pauling to put the greatest weight on this trial, but his error was to extrapolate the findings to the general population. The other trial on which Pauling put great weight was the Cowan et al. trial (1942; Table) which was carried out with schoolchildren during the war years and probably the dietary vitamin C intake was low and in this respect the benefit may be explained by the correction of marginal deficiency as in the UK studies with schoolboys and male students (Hemilä 1997).

As regards the errors in Pauling's quantitative conclusions, it should obviously be taken into account that essentially all of the trials available today were carried out after Pauling worked on the topic and, even more importantly, were carried out precisely because Pauling popularized the topic (Figure). Without bold conjectures, progress in science is slow or non-existent, and in this respect the accuracy of Pauling's extrapolation from the single placebo-controlled trial using regular 1 g/day supplementation available to him in the early 1970s is of secondary concern. Furthermore, Pauling's own view of science was that an occasional mistake, even when published, was not as bad as lowering one's sights to less challenging research (Lipscomb 1994).

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Short summary of Apple's arguments:
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8779885>

Rima Apple reviewed the history of vitamins in the USA in the 20th century and described a number of interesting patterns in the discussions about vitamins. She did not take a particular stand on the question of whether vitamins are useful, harmful, or neutral, but instead analyzed the political views and discussions on the topic.

According to Apple, the concern about America's nutrition was not a concept generated by pharmaceutical companies pushing vitamin supplements. By the late 1930s, several studies documented the nation's poor diet, including eating vitamin poor foods, modern processing destroying parts of vitamins, and poor diets due to the Great Depression. These issues were well reported in the popular press in the early part of the previous century, and this context led to the origin of the vitamin industry. Thus, while many of the more recent advertisements are exaggerated and mislead consumers, the concern about nutrition among lay people originated from scientific findings that were reported in the popular press. Apple also reported that many researchers found that workers receiving vitamins had considerably lower rates of absenteeism, stayed in their jobs longer, and even scored higher on their merit ratings.

Apple points out that Linus Pauling, a chemist, biochemist, and peace activist, was not the first to consider vitamins for preventing and curing the common cold. Popular literature and advertisements linked subclinical vitamin deficiency and respiratory infections much earlier, and that was justified by papers in medical literature. In any case, Pauling received two Nobel Prizes and he was widely featured in the popular media...

According to Apple, these ad hominem attacks on Pauling made his opponents look petty. Their position was further undermined by the reams of conflicting data published in the popular press. If physicians, those who put themselves forth as experts, cannot agree, then maybe Pauling, a brilliant scientist, had a point (Apple p. 84)...

The negative view of the AMA against vitamins traces back a century. In her history of vitamins in the USA, Apple described that "the American Medical Association (AMA) was most critical of the emerging [vitamin] industry. In articles and in editorials, starting as early as 1922, the organization called the commercial hype surrounding vitamins 'a gigantic fraud'" (Apple 1996 p. 8). Over and over again, the AMA campaigned against vitamin supplements, insisting that a diet lacking vitamins would give rise to gross vitamin-deficiency diseases, and that these conditions were the concern of the doctor.

Anonymous (1975) Downgrading vitamin C. *TIME Magazine* (Mar 24)
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Ever since Linus Pauling proposed in 1970 that large doses of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) would prevent or cure the common cold, sales of the vitamin have soared, despite the widely expressed doubts of other researchers. Three reports now cast a further shadow on Pauling's theory. In one of two studies published in the A.M.A. Journal, 311 volunteers at the National Institutes of Health took part in an experiment in which about half were given one gram of vitamin C three times daily for a nine-month period; the remainder took a placebo under the same circumstances. If a volunteer showed signs of coming down with a cold, the dosage of pills—whether vitamin C or placebo—was increased by three grams per day. N.I.H. researchers report that the effects of the vitamin on the number of colds "seem to be nil" and the effects on severity of the colds are clinically insignificant. In the second Journal report, researchers at the University of Chicago say that after a review of various studies of vitamin C conducted from 1939 to 1973, there is little convincing evidence of the vitamin's effectiveness in preventing or curing colds. Moreover, they find evidence that large daily doses may even be medically harmful, producing diarrhea or kidney stones.

Response by Pauling (1975a) *TIME Magazine* (Mar 31)
<https://time.com/archive/6817175/forum-the-cold-war>

The American Medical Association continues its unjustified effort to downgrade vitamin C [March 24]. The effectiveness of vitamin C against the common cold is not nil, as stated by the A.M.A. Instead, every one of the twelve controlled studies that have been carried out in which subjects were exposed to cold viruses by contact with other people and in which some subjects regularly received the vitamin C, an average of 1,000 mg. per day, and others received an inactive tablet, gave the result that the vitamin-C subjects had less illness than the controls. The average amount of decreased illness for the vitamin-C subjects was 37%. There is no doubt that vitamin C, taken regularly or taken in large amounts at the first sign of a cold, leads to significant protection against colds for most people.

The A.M.A. spokesmen ignored three of the important studies and misrepresented the others. They also mentioned the possibility of serious adverse side effects but referred to them as hypothetical. The danger of forming kidney stones has been greatly exaggerated. Vitamin C is a much safer substance than ordinary cold medicines; moreover, it can stop a cold, whereas ordinary cold medicines cannot.

Linus Pauling

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Text p.77:

Pharmacological Intakes of Ascorbic Acid:

Intakes of ascorbic acid far in excess of physiological requirements (1 g/day or more) have been reported to have some effect in reducing the frequency and severity of symptoms of the common cold and other winter illness (Pauling, 1971... several reviewers (Chalmers, 1975; Dykes and Meier, 1975) believe that these benefits of large doses of ascorbic acid are too small to justify recommending routine intake of large amounts by the entire population.

FNB [Food and Nutrition Board, National Research Council] (1989) Recommended Dietary Allowances, 10th edn. Washington DC: National Academy Press
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Text p.120:

Pharmacologic Intakes and Toxicity:

Daily intakes of ascorbic acid of 1 g or more have been reported to reduce the frequency and severity of symptoms of the common cold and other respiratory illnesses (Pauling, 1971)... Several reviewers (Chalmers, 1975; Dykes and Meier, 1975) have concluded that any benefits of large doses of ascorbic acid for these conditions are too small to justify recommending routine intake of large amounts by the entire population.

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